

Review

Challenges and potential pathways towards sustainable agriculture within the European Green Deal

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HIGHLIGHTS

- We review policy instruments, key-challenges and approaches to attain sustainable agricultural systems within the Green Deal.
- Challenges include reduced yields, land demand, nitrogen needs, changes in diet, food waste, distribution and access to food, and externalities.
- Integration of different approaches to sustainable agriculture is required to optimize a range of ecosystem services
- This requires changes in the food system, from land management to distribution, diets, education and spatial optimization
- Actors supporting the transition through increased delivery of ecosystem services need socioeconomic recognition

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

CONTEXT: Agriculture plays a central role in the European Green Deal with various policies and strategies converging to promote sustainable agriculture and food systems. The Farm to Fork strategy approaches agriculture from a sustainable food systems perspective. Sustainable agriculture is also central in the European Biodiversity strategy, in the Long-term vision for EU Rural areas and in the Soil strategy. Despite clear policy objectives, there is still a long way towards an effective transition towards sustainable agriculture based on integrated, science based, solutions.

OBJECTIVE: This paper aims to contribute to the debate on the challenges and opportunities for the transition towards a sustainable agriculture in Europe, the role of European policies and practical approaches.

METHODS: We reviewed policy documents, scientific literature and global data to reflect on the vision of the Farm to Fork and other European strategies affecting sustainable agriculture, focussing on which **policy instruments** are foreseen to reach their objectives, which are the **key-challenges** related to achieve more sustainable farming, and on possible **approaches** to attain sustainable agriculture.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS: We provide an overview of synergies and shared objectives between different European policies and strategies aiming to support the transition to sustainable agriculture from environmental, social and economic perspectives. We identified several often reported challenges to attain sustainable food systems: reduced yields, increased land demand, nitrogen needs, changes in diet, food waste, distribution and

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access to food, and externalities to third countries. Finally, we discuss two main approaches to sustainable agriculture with potential complementarity to fulfil the objectives of sustainable agriculture as reflected in the different European policies and strategies. Sustainable intensification with focus on environmental- friendly production, and agroecology with focus on ecology, social justice and food sovereignty. We reflect on how both approaches can be integrated to create synergies and optimize delivery of multiple ecosystem services. The transformation to sustainable agriculture, as expected from the several revised strategies, is not just a technical question of farming practices, but requires a holistic approach considering social, economic, cultural, technical and environmental aspects. Local adaptations, stakeholder participation, and recognition that agriculture produces more than crops, are key to support this transition of agriculture and food systems.

SIGNIFICANCE: The transition towards more sustainable agriculture requires alignment of policies related to social, economic and environmental aspects, including social and economic acknowledgment to farmers, as managers of agroecosystems and cultural landscapes delivering a range of ecosystem services.

1. Introduction

The European Green Deal (EGD), which proposes to achieve a climate-neutral Europe by 2050, puts a strong focus on the transition to a more sustainable agriculture and food system in order to contribute to climate change mitigation and protection of biodiversity. The European Commission wants to reduce the emissions 50–55% compared to 1990's (European Commission, 2020a) and the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy aims to ensure that agriculture, fisheries, aquaculture and food chain contributes significantly to this target. The EGD explains that strategic changes would be necessary across a wide range of activities to meet the climate and biodiversity crises. Food, agriculture, and wider land and resource management are all foreseen to require changes in the desired direction that is de-intensifying some production systems (Buckwell et al., 2022). Since agriculture is the second sector responsible for greenhouse gas emissions (11%) in the European Union (EU), ahead of the industrial sector (9%) (European Environmental Agency, 2021), the transformation of the agricultural sector towards a more sustainable and climate-friendly agriculture could largely contribute to achieve the objectives of the Green Deal.

Between 1990 and 2019, a 28% decrease of emissions took place in Europe (Fig. 1), with reductions in all sectors except transport and air conditioning, and the largest reduction in manufacturing industries. In the agricultural sector the decrease was 20.5% due mainly to the decrease in cattle population (28%) and in the quantities of applied synthetic (25%) and organic (13%) fertilizers (European Environmental Agency, 2021). The specific subsectors of enteric fermentation and direct emissions from agricultural soils were responsible of a 4.3% decrease of total emissions between 1990 and 2019, and they are among the sectors that have reduced their emissions the most, comparable to the reduction of the cement, aluminium and fluorochemical industry together. Despite this, enteric fermentation still contributes with more than 40% to all agricultural emissions nowadays, while the remaining emissions in the agricultural sector are mostly related to the management of soils (fertilizers), crops and residues (Fig. 2).

To understand agricultural systems and identify more sustainable forms of production, it is important to recognize that agroecosystems produce much more than crops (Dale and Polasky, 2007), and that rural lands can provide much more than agricultural produce (Gawith and Hodge, 2019). In the last decade a large effort to change our vision on

Fig. 1. Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions (in CO₂-eq including indirect emissions) in the EU from 1990 to 2019. (Own elaboration based on data from European Environmental Agency, 2021).

agriculture and rural development was carried out by part of the scientific community, trying to change the paradigm from optimization of agricultural productivity to management of agroecosystems that provide a range of ecosystem services (Albaladejo et al., 2021; Almagro et al., 2016; Dale and Polasky, 2007; de Groot et al., 2022). Agriculture, and ecosystem services provided by agroecosystems, are increasingly at the intersection of several European strategies and policies, particularly within the Green Deal, like the Farm to Fork strategy (F2F, European Commission, 2020a), the Biodiversity strategy (BS, European Commission, 2020b), and the Soil strategy for 2030 (SS, European Commission, 2021b). But sustainable agriculture is also central to other European policies such as the Long-term vision for EU rural areas (LTVRA, European Commission, 2021a) and the EU Mission a Soil Deal for Europe (European Commission, 2020d). The overarching goal of all of these strategies and policies is to make agricultural production more sustainable for healthy diets in healthy soils, contribute to climate change mitigation and protecting biodiversity in valued and well integrated rural areas, considering social justice leaving no one behind.

Agroecosystems interact with natural systems in the provision of services to the society. However, the current intensive agro-industrial system of food production and consumption is not sustainable since it does not consider these interactions and is largely responsible for environmental disasters and land degradation including loss of soil organic matter and soil biodiversity, soil erosion and floods, over-exploitation, contamination and eutrophication of surface and groundwater resources, land levelling, and removal of vegetation (Álvarez-Rogel et al., 2020) (Fig. 3).

When agroecosystems are well maintained, they serve society and human well-being by generating a range of ecosystem services, many of which are based on soil functions (Luján Soto et al., 2020), biodiversity,

landscape characteristics, and traditional knowledge (de Groot et al., 2022). The European Green Deal and its Farm to Fork, Biodiversity, and Soil strategy, provide clear policy objectives and targets to de-intensify production systems, making them less dependent on external inputs (Buckwell et al., 2022), and promoting ecosystem services that rural areas and agricultural systems provide to society. For instance, with 40% of the land dedicated to agriculture, rural areas are active players in the European green and digital transitions through food production, preservation of biodiversity and fight against climate change (European Commission, 2021a). Moreover, farmers have a key role preserving biodiversity through sustainable agriculture, and at the same time biodiversity improves agricultural productivity providing safe, sustainable, nutritious and affordable food (European Commission, 2020b).

To understand delivery of ecosystem services from agriculture it is important to understand the continuous interaction between agricultural and natural ecosystems: (i) well-managed agroecosystems generate beneficial ecosystem services such as soil retention, food production, and aesthetic or cultural values that reduce human pressure on natural systems; (ii) agroecosystems receive beneficial ecosystem services from other ecosystems such as pollination from non-agricultural ecosystems or water supply from surface and groundwater; and (iii) ecosystem services from non-agricultural systems may be impacted by agricultural practices leading to disservices from agriculture (Dale and Polasky, 2007; Zabala et al., 2021).

This paper aims to contribute to the debate on the challenges and opportunities for a transition towards a sustainable European agriculture. We focus our evaluation on (i) the role and integration of the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy, the Biodiversity strategy (BS), the Soil Strategy (SS) and the Long Term Vision for EU Rural Areas (LTVRA), as the main current European *strategies* affecting agriculture (besides the Common

Fig. 2. Emissions in the agricultural sector (in % of kt CO₂-eq year⁻¹) in the EU averaged from 2000 to 2018. (Own elaboration; Data source: European Environmental Agency (2021).

Fig. 3. Agricultural fields with intensive horticulture based on high agrochemical and water inputs around the Mar Menor lagoon (SE Spain). The Mar Menor lagoon is an example of a highly eutrophized system due to the intensity of activities in its catchment area, which nowadays represent a heavy negative impact for local population and for the sustainability of the tourism-based economy around the lagoon (Photo: Carolina Boix-Fayos).

Agricultural Policy), and (ii) the potential practical **approaches** of agricultural systems that could help to reach sustainable farming and the objectives defined in these strategies and policies.

2. Methods

The paper is approached as a reflection on the challenges and pathways of the European agriculture transition within the Green Deal, based on an integrative review (Broome, 2000; Torraco, 2016) synthesizing knowledge and information from three sources:

1. Review of policy documents: the Farm to Fork strategy (F2F) (European Commission, 2020a), the Biodiversity strategy of the EC (BS) (European Commission, 2020b), the main Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) reforms to fit the Green Deal (European Commission, 2020c), the Long-Term Vision for EU Rural Areas (LTVRA) (European Commission, 2021a), the Food Waste Index Report (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021) and the Annual European Union greenhouse gas inventory 1990–2019 and inventory report (European Environmental Agency, 2021).
2. Review of scientific literature: after identification of challenges to the EU sustainable agriculture transition from the relevant European strategies and policies, we reviewed additional scientific literature using the following search terms: “agroecology”, “sustainable land management”, “sustainable agricultural practices”, “sustainable intensification”, “food waste”, “sustainable diets” and “externalization of agricultural costs”. Those terms were used independently and in combination with “Green Deal”, focussing the analysis on review and conceptual papers.
3. Review of global data: data from evaluation reports were extracted and elaborated to further understand the present day situation regarding the context of transition to sustainable agriculture. Those data were extracted from the Food Waste Index Report (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021), the Annual European Union greenhouse gas inventory 1990–2019 and inventory report (European Environmental Agency, 2021), and the Factsheet to make the CAP reform fit for the European Green Deal.

The paper is further organized in three main sections: policies and strategies supporting the transition to a greener agriculture (Section 3); challenges to the transition to more sustainable farming (Section 4) and potential approaches to support the transition (Section 5).

3. European policies and strategies supporting sustainable agriculture

At the core of the European Green Deal to aspire to be the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, there are three statements: no net

emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, economic growth decoupled from resource use, and no person and no place left behind. Agriculture plays a central role in each of these three statements. The transition to a more sustainable agriculture and food system is one of the prime objectives of the Green Deal through its Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy, the Biodiversity strategy (BS) and the Soil strategy (SS). In other policy initiatives like the Common Agricultural policy (CAP) reform and the Long Term Vision for EU Rural Areas (LTVRA) the transition to more sustainable agriculture also takes a central role. Moreover, the ‘EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe’ promotes research and innovation to provide innovative solutions for sustainable agriculture contributing to healthier soils. Together, these interacting policies and strategies should provide the instruments to facilitate the transition to more sustainable agriculture and support the objectives of the Green Deal. The following paragraphs analyse the role of each of the policies and strategies and their possible synergies and interactions.

3.1. F2F and the CAP

The F2F strategy (European Commission, 2020a) aims to promote a transition to a greener way of farming based on the premise that that there is an urgent need to reduce dependency on pesticides, antimicrobials, and fertilizers, and increase organic farming, improve animal welfare and reverse biodiversity loss. It proposes to achieve a minimum of 25% organic farming in Europe, reduce the use of pesticides by 50% and the use of fertilizers by 20%, all in less than a decade (2030). It fosters the transition to sustainable food systems, although the concept of sustainable remains ambiguous and some authors point out that no clear conceptual boundaries are established, with many objectives and topics not translated into specific actions (Schebesta and Candel, 2020). The F2F strategy acknowledges that this transition will not happen without a shift in people’s diet. Thus, the transition proposed by the F2F strategy involves the entire value chain, including society and their choices of consumption, considering their crucial role to incentivize and support the change. Since market demand has a strong impact on what and how food is produced, measures beyond the agricultural sector, like responsible and conscious consumption and education, are key to promote the transition to sustainable food systems (Morais et al., 2021).

The F2F strategy indicates four main transition paths or tools to accomplish its objectives: (i) adapting directives (i.e. sustainable use of pesticides), (ii) enforcing relevant environmental and climate legislation (i.e. controlling reduced fertilizer use); (iii) developing specific action plans (i.e. integrated nutrient management action plan, action plan for organic farming); and (iv) adapting the new CAP to the objectives of the Green Deal (i.e. inclusion of targeted measures in the CAP national strategic plans).

In all four transition paths, the new CAP (2023–27) is a key instrument to link the F2F strategy objectives to action on the ground by the

farmers and land managers. The new CAP focusses on ten objectives linked directly to the Green Deal and to EU sustainability goals of agriculture and rural areas. The idea is that the new CAP works as incentive and empowerment to European farmers to contribute more decisively to tackling climate change, protecting the environment and making the transition to more sustainable and resilient food systems (European Commission, 2020c). The new CAP will be implemented at the national level with national strategic plans (Nadeu et al., 2023) and tools focussed on reaching the same environmental and climate objectives contributing to the European Green Deal. In total, 40% of the CAP budget will be climate-relevant (European Commission, 2020d). The new CAP is based on a “Green Architecture” where all beneficiaries of the CAP will continue to have their payments linked to a set of mandatory rules (“conditionality”), in addition to statutory management requirements (SMRs), that apply to all farmers whether or not they receive support under the CAP. Farmers receiving CAP support are expected to comply with good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAECs) and voluntary “ecoschemes” (mandatory for national strategic plans but voluntary for farmers) will unlock new funding and additional incentives for climate and environmental friendly practices. At the moment of writing this paper, 28 Strategic Plans defining the ecosystems at national level were submitted and reviewed by the EC, waiting for approval. Across Europe, these plans foresee 184 ecosystems to incentivize practices ranging from precision agriculture to cover crops, agro-ecology, carbon farming and agroforestry (European Commission, 2022).

Furthermore, to fit the Green Deal, the CAP reform includes promotion of the adoption of findings from research and innovation by farmers and delivering up-to date technological and scientific information to advice farmers, which can be understood as the promotion of extension services. Altogether, the new CAP is expected to make a substantial contribution to the targets of the F2F and Biodiversity strategies, if the Strategic Plans of the Member States are able to reflect these

targets (European Commission, 2020c).

In addition to purely environmental objectives, the CAP reform also aims for a better distribution of income support by establishing a maximum of 100.000 € per year of subsidies per beneficiary. This should prevent to continue with the current situation in which at least 80% of CAP payments go to less than 20% of beneficiaries (Fig. 4) and 63% of the EU countries distribute more than 70% of direct payments among the 20% biggest farmers. This measure is expected to support social justice and socioeconomic development as foreseen in the Long Term Vision for EU Rural areas.

3.2. Integration of other European strategies to support sustainable agriculture

Beyond the F2F, several other European strategies are relevant for the transition to sustainable agriculture, although each with a different focus: the Long-Term Vision for the EU’s Rural Areas (LTVRA), the Biodiversity strategy (BS) and the Soil strategy (SS). The LTVRA is part of the Commission’s political priorities together with the digital transition, the green transition (Green Deal) and the European recovery plan after the covid-19 pandemic, and focusses on social and economic aspects and the identity of rural areas (Fig. 5). It is a medium-term strategy (2040) that looks to restore the appreciation of the role and importance of rural areas through reinforcing its identity based on the diversity of the landscape, the culture and the heritage. The LTVRA recognizes that 40% of rural areas are used for agriculture and are key to maintaining food security. Across Europe, agriculture represents 12% of all jobs and 4% of gross added value (European Commission, 2021a). Rural areas are responsible for food production and management of natural resources and protection of natural and cultural landscapes. This makes rural development central to the success of the other two strategies: F2F and SS.

The Soil strategy (SS) focusses on *Soil Health* and is directly linked to

Fig. 4. Share of direct payments and land covered by 20% of beneficiaries by Member State in 2018. (Own elaboration based on data in European Commission, 2020c).

Fig. 5. (A) Overview of how four main European policies and strategies related to the Green Deal support the transition to more sustainable agriculture (red central box) and link with the three pillars of sustainability (B) Focus (blue circles) and action areas (blue rectangles) of each of the four European strategies with direct impact on agriculture. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the Green Deal and F2F strategy, while supporting also the objectives from the Biodiversity strategy. It sets out a framework including concrete measures to protect and restore soils and ensure that they are used sustainably, protecting biodiversity. The SS defines a vision and sets objectives to achieve healthy soils by 2050, with concrete actions by 2030, including the development of a Soil Health Law to ensure environmental and health protection (European Commission, 2021b). The ‘EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe’ support the SS through research and innovation, for example to identify more sustainable agriculture and supporting business models. The BS, with short-term objectives by 2030, aims for restoration of carbon rich habitats and a climate friendly agriculture. Its focus is on *Biodiversity* and *Natural capital*. It states that biodiversity loss threatens our food system and that biodiversity improves agricultural productivity. The BS aims to bring nature back to agricultural land and acknowledges the vital role of farmers preserving biodiversity. The concept of sustainable agriculture is central to the four strategies to reach their objectives, but mentioned in different ways (e.g. fully sustainable practices on agriculture, sustainable food production, sustainable soil management). All four strategies are aligned with the three pillars of sustainability (Fig. 5).

4. What are the key-challenges for the transition to sustainable farming?

Several strongly related key-challenges can be foreseen for the transition from conventional to organic, greener or more sustainable farming systems. Some of those challenges were identified during the review of the strategies and related scientific papers, and are therefore

key for the success of the Green Deal. Fig. 6 visualizes how each of the challenges relates to the 13 action areas of the strategies as expressed in Fig. 5. Among all the possible challenges we highlight the following:

1. **Maintaining yields.** After the price inflation of food commodities in 2007 and 2008, the “food security” concept became again an urgent issue on the geopolitical agenda. From the FAO Rome Summit on World Food Security two key concepts were highlighted: food production needed to increase 50% by 2030, and food production needed to be doubled by 2050 to feed 9 billion people on the planet (Maye and Kirwan, 2013). Although this figure was later corrected to 70%, and estimates were surrounded by high levels of uncertainty and assumptions (Tomlinson, 2013). Nevertheless, a key question regarding food security and the implementation of the F2F Strategy is if a 25% increase in European organic agriculture will be able to produce sufficient yields to feed the population. Some studies indicated an average decrease of yields between 20% (Badgley et al., 2007; De Ponti et al., 2012) and 35% (Kirchmann, 2019) under organic agriculture as compared to conventional farming. Some studies also reported a lower stability of yields (–15%) under organic farming, although this effect might be reduced using green manure and enhanced fertilisation (Knapp and van der Heijden, 2018). Recently (Beckman et al., 2020) predicted a decrease of yields between 7 and 12% with the input reduction proposed in the F2F strategy, but without taking into account increased land in organic production and reduction of food waste. On the other hand, Badgley et al. (2007) stated that organic agriculture can provide enough calories to support the whole human population eating with the diets

Fig. 6. Overview of the relation between the main identified challenges and the 13 action areas of the four studied strategies.

of 2007. This conclusion was based on a global dataset of 293 yield ratios for plant and animal production (Badgley et al., 2007), although these findings were questioned by others (Avery, 2007). This challenge is related with many of the actions of the 4 studied strategies: organic agriculture is directly related with soil health and increase of biodiversity (actions 1–6) and with actions related to food security (focus 8–9) and with actions 12 and 13 for protection and enhancement of rural areas (Fig. 6).

2. **Nitrogen needs.** One of the main restrictions of organic agriculture is the use of mineral fertilizers, thus adequate nitrogen supply is challenging (Muller et al., 2017). To compensate, rotations with legumes are often used for biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) to supply nitrogen for the growth of non-legume crops, either in situ or in imported manure. Consequently, this implies a smaller available area for the main crops and reduces the overall productivity of organic compared to conventional agriculture. This challenge is related to the same actions of the former one (Fig. 6) and to action 7 because of the high sensitivity of water resources to excess of nitrogen.
3. **Land demand.** If we assume that organic agriculture produces less yields, more land is needed to produce the same amount of yield (Muller et al., 2017). Based on the rotations with legumes for N fixation, 1.6 units of additional land are needed per unit of conventional land (Connor, 2018) to produce the same yield as with conventional agriculture. Expansion of arable land is however not an effective option to reduce the environmental impact of conventional agriculture. Land use changes to expand agricultural land — converting forests, grassland, or wetland into arable land — result in lost products (timber, fiber, energy, etc.) and lost ecosystem services (sequestered carbon in soil and vegetation, water regulation, biodiversity, etc.). Given the wide range of environmental challenges and constraints (e.g. increasing competition for land from other human activities, importance of ecological functions of unfarmed land, degradation of vast areas due to unsustainable land management practices, negative effects of agriculture on biodiversity), expanding agricultural land is not seen as an ecological and feasible option (Bernard and Lux, 2017). Reducing the food-competing feed from arable land in combination with reduced production and

consumption of animal products, would allow to allocate more land for organic agriculture for human consumption. Therefore, to feed the 2050 world population in a sustainable way, a well-designed food system with increased land to organic agriculture, reduced animal number and animal food consumption and reduced food waste need to be jointly addressed (Muller et al., 2017). This challenge is related to actions trying to keep land in a good natural condition (Actions 1, 3 and 7) and sustainable food production and reducing waste (Focus 10 and 11) (Fig. 6).

4. **Changes in diet.** Reducing global average demand for animal products and their share in human diets is a strategy for more sustainable food systems based on rationalised use of natural resources, reduced environmental impacts, and protection of human health (Muller et al., 2017). However dietary changes are not enough to achieve sustainable food systems. Reducing food waste and losses and changes in crop production and livestock need to be carried out to keep food systems within the planet boundaries (Westhoek et al., 2021). Organic agriculture combined with reduced animal numbers in livestock production and reduced food competing feed requirements, can provide a promising part of the solution for more sustainable agricultural production, food supply and consumption. Between 1990 and 2019 most European countries have experienced an important reduction in cattle (−28% on average), with the exception of Cyprus, Finland, Ireland, Slovenia, Spain and Iceland (European Environmental Agency, 2021; Fig. 7). Model estimates show that organic agriculture can probably feed the world population of 9.2 billion in 2050, if relatively modest diets are adopted (Erb et al., 2009). Besides, there is also a relation between production and diet, so agriculture needs to be nutrition sensitive, not focussing only on few species, and attend nutrition deficits to overcome hunger and obesity (Pretty and Bharucha, 2014). High quality diets produce less cropland waste but more agricultural inputs in form of water, fertilizers and pesticides, due to the fact that production of fruits and vegetables need less land and higher inputs (Conrad et al., 2018). This points to the need to invert this relationship, relating high quality diets to more efficient use of agricultural inputs. Again legumes can help here, providing N to soils, as explained above and

Fig. 7. Percentage of change of cattle between 1990 and 2019 versus percentage of change of total GHG emissions in the same period. (Own elaboration; Data source: [European Environmental Agency, 2021](#)).

Fig. 8. Estimates of Food Waste based on the Food Waste Index at the later stage of the food waste journey: household, food service and retail (Own elaboration; Data source: [United Nations Environment Programme, 2021](#)).

assuring a rich-protein diet (Cusworth et al., 2021). This challenge is related to action areas 2,4,10 and 11 (Fig. 6).

5. **Food waste.** There are several causes for food waste related to the food industry such as processing problems and lack of appropriate planning. Food consumption patterns also play a key role for sustainable agriculture with regard to food wastage. Conrad et al. (2018) found that the average US consumer produces a food waste equivalent to 30% of the calories available for consumption per day, a quarter of daily food available for consumption and a 7% of annual cropland. From the approximately one-third of the food produced globally that is not consumed, around a 14% corresponds to post-harvest loss. This is a practice, mainly used in relatively rich countries, to control the market prices, preventing that the prices get below production costs. This practice has a high environmental impact due to a depletion of natural resources that finally do not contribute to the market and are often produced unsustainably with high inputs from water, nutrients and agrochemicals (Martínez-Valderrama et al., 2020).

A recent study of United Nations Environment Programme (2021) estimated that 931 millions of tonnes of food waste were produced in 2019 globally, of which 61% came from households, 26% from foodservices and 13% from retail. It estimates also that household food waste per capita is broadly similar across countries income groups and is equally relevant in high, upper-middle and lower-middle income countries. In Europe, the highest household food waste per capita are found in Greece and Malta with estimates above 100 kg per capita year⁻¹ (Fig. 8).

Reducing food waste thus offers a complementary approach to reducing resource use and reducing the environmental impact of agriculture. This challenge is related to action areas of the 2, 6, 9, 10 and 11 of the four strategies studied (Fig. 6).

6. **Distribution and access to food.** Besides production, the distribution and access to food are key aspects to feed the world population. This broader understanding of solutions to prevent hunger, although widely recognized, is not included in the dominant framing of food security focussing on production aspects (Tomlinson, 2013). Beckman et al. (2020) predict an increased food insecurity (22 million people more compared to no adoption scenarios) following the adoption of agricultural input reductions proposed in the F2F strategy due to higher commodity prices and a reduction in income (reduction of trade), particularly in Africa. However, this analysis only takes into account agricultural input reductions, disregarding other measures to incentivize better food distribution and changing consumption patterns that may lead to reduced food insecurity and more jobs and income. This challenge is related to action areas 8 and 9 (Fig. 6).
7. **Externalities.** The risk of externalising the damage caused by intensive agriculture to other countries is one of the main risks of agricultural strategies supported by the Green Deal, pointed out by Fuchs et al. (2020). According to those authors, EU member states are taking the risk to outsource environmental damage to other countries, while taking the credit for green policies at home (Action 12, Fig. 6). For instance, Fuchs et al. (2020) explain how compared to the European Union, pesticide and herbicide use and deforestation are higher in several countries outside the EU supplying oilseeds to the region. The EU acknowledges the risk of externalities in the F2F strategy, recognizing that the EU food system should be accompanied by policies that help raise environmental and social production standards globally, to avoid the externalization and export of unsustainable practices (Actions 8 and 11, Fig. 6).

5. Potential approaches for the transition to a greener agriculture

Over the past decades, a wide range of approaches to sustainable farming have emerged, ranging from sustainable intensification,

ecological intensification (Tittone, 2014), and agroecology, to regenerative agriculture (Luján Soto et al., 2021b; Tittone et al., 2022), nature positive farming, sustainable land management, carbon farming and many more. While there are important differences between most of these approaches, and some of them still lack clear definitions (Schreefel et al., 2020; Giller et al., 2021; Buckwell et al., 2022; Tittone et al., 2022), there are also many similarities. Some approaches are more holistic than others, including not only sustainable farming practices but also measures further down the value chain, including socioeconomic and political objectives such as food sovereignty and fair working conditions for farmers (Anderson and Rivera-Ferre, 2021). All these initiatives reflect a growing concern about the sustainability of agricultural systems in relation to climate regulation (Aguilera et al., 2020) and to the provision of ecosystem services (Dale and Polasky, 2007; Gawith and Hodge, 2019). Increasingly, the analysis of agro-food systems and approaches to sustainable farming also recognize the importance to articulate actionable knowledge built on the combination of cutting-edge science and experiential, indigenous and traditional knowledge (Webb and Sonnino, 2021). In this section we highlight Agroecology (AE) and Sustainable Intensification (SI) as representative of two models towards sustainable agriculture, with different approaches in between as mentioned above including different elements of each. Agroecological approaches have been highlighted by the Farm-to-Fork and the Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020b) as means to contribute to achieve the objectives of the Green Deal (Tataridas et al., 2022; Rööös et al., 2022) since the cornerstones of the agroecological approach are very well reflected in many of the strategies that form the Green Deal (Gargano et al., 2021). Other authors and collectives are more supportive of increasing sustainability of intensive agriculture through sustainable intensification (Beltrán et al., 2021). Both models represent different approaches for a transition to more sustainable agriculture as aimed for by the different strategies of the Green Deal (F2F, BS, SS) and other European priority policies (LTRVA). Both AE and SI show similarities but also important differences and possible complementarities to support the transition towards sustainable production. Both approaches are based on good agricultural practices to reduce the need for external inputs and reducing the impacts on the environment and public health. However, the two approaches are increasingly discussed and often considered as opposed paradigms (Bernard and Lux, 2017). While the main focus of SI is on optimizing the efficiency of large scale agriculture production to reduce negative environmental and social impacts (Fig. 9), AE takes a more holistic approach by considering practical, social and political aspects of sustainable farming systems in the context of the entire food system, including agricultural supply chains, consumers, and the socio-political movement required to promote its implementation. Although AE is often associated with smallholder farming, there is increasing interest in testing its viability for larger scale implementation and in finding approaches to support scaling, recognizing that AE is by definition adapted to local environmental, socioeconomic and cultural contexts (Ferguson et al., 2019).

SI and AE both aim at achieving food security and reducing negative impacts on the environment. SI has been widely adopted by international research, policy and international development organisations and by the private sector, that has also been criticized for its focus on the production-side. AE is frequently presented as an environmentally sound counterexample based on a holistic approach emphasizing social aspects of the food system, that is however often questioned regarding scalability to feed a growing population (Bernard and Lux, 2017). In the next two paragraphs we further discuss how both systems approach sustainable agriculture and which are their possible complementarities that can support the transition towards more sustainable farming systems.

5.1. Sustainable intensification

Sustainable intensification (SI), could be summarized by the lemma

Fig. 9. A. Intensive agricultural landscape in SE Spain. Soil and water conservation terraces were levelled and substituted by alleys to facilitate mechanized labour and intensive agricultural management with high inputs of water, fertilizers and pesticides. Citrus trees are cultivated on ridges between the alleys. In the Diverfarming research project (www.diverfarming.eu), a diversification experiment was tested in this area introducing an intercropping in the alleys with rotation of fava beans in winter (B) and vetch and barley in spring (C) in order to improve soil quality and biodiversity, to facilitate infiltration and reduce erosion rates. Intercropping practices to diversify monocultures could help the transition to sustainable or ecological intensification systems to help reaching the objectives of several EC strategies (F2F, BS, SS) (Martínez-Mena et al., 2021) (Photos: Carolina Boix-Fayos).

“Feed the world sustainably” (Bernard and Lux, 2017). Its main objective is to increase agricultural output levels per area unit while reducing natural (e.g. land and water) and synthetic (e.g. fertilizers, pesticides) inputs by using them more efficiently and thereby reducing the negative impacts on the environment (Pretty et al., 2011; Pretty and Bharucha, 2014). It is a relatively open concept that emphasizes ends rather than means, and does not pre-determine technologies, species mix or particular design components (Pretty and Bharucha, 2014). SI is open to the inclusion of different approaches and may include agricultural practices proposed in agroecology. This broad description also makes it subject to a wide range of interpretations and applications. It involves the broader food system, acknowledging that food security cannot be achieved by food production alone and there is a growing consensus that issues such as waste, consumption and distribution need also be considered. By coupling the terms “sustainable” and “intensification”, critics accuse SI of enabling greenwashing of agribusiness companies and business-as-usual large-scale industrial agriculture (Bernard and Lux, 2017). Therefore, often the alternative “ecological intensification” is used, putting more emphasis on the use of natural functionalities of ecosystems aiming at designing multifunctional agroecosystems that are both sustained by nature and sustainable in their nature (Tittonell, 2014).

Following the definition proposed by (Pretty and Bharucha, 2014), SI should: (1) utilize crop varieties and livestock breeds with a high ratio of productivity to the use of externally and internally derived inputs, (2)

avoid the unnecessary use of external inputs, (3) harness agroecological processes such as nutrient cycling, biological nitrogen fixation, allelopathy, predation and parasitism, (4) minimize use of technologies or practices that have adverse impacts on the environment and human health, (5) make productive use of human capital in the form of knowledge and capacity to adapt and innovate; and (6) minimize the impacts of system management on externalities such as GHG emissions, contamination of surface and groundwater, loss of biodiversity, and dispersal of pests, pathogens and weeds.

Sustainable Intensification could promote transitions towards greener economies under a very wide umbrella of practices. Some authors include under this umbrella, for instance gene-editing techniques, indoor farming technologies (vertical farming) (Fuchs et al., 2020) as well as some agroecological practices, agroforestry and integrated pest management. Besides optimizing productivity per unit area, important challenges for SI remain to guarantee minimal environmental impact, a fair production process of safe, healthy and nutritious food and not to become a marketing instrument for “green washing” unsustainable production methods.

5.2. Agroecology

Agroecology (AE) can be characterised by the lemma “Helping the world feed itself” (Bernard and Lux, 2017). The principles of AE are well defined and documented (Wezel et al., 2009). In short, AE is defined as

“the science of applying ecological concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable food systems” (Gliessman, 2015). It is described as an environmentally sound coexistence of agriculture and biodiversity in the same area, which aims to improve agricultural systems by mimicking and enhancing natural processes of the ecosystem. AE strongly builds on traditional and local knowledge following a bottom-up approach integrating knowledge from different fields (local, traditional and scientific knowledge from environmental and social sciences) and promoting horizontal learning and sharing of experiences through farmer field schools and farmer-to-farmer networks (Gliessman, 2015), or Living Labs as proposed in the F2F strategy. AE clearly goes beyond farming systems and consists of three pillars: science, practices, and social-political movement (Wezel et al., 2009). The social pillar aims to improve livelihoods of farming households through reduced costs (minimisation of the expenses for expensive inputs), increased yields, improved nutrition and empowerment of women (De Schutter, 2014). AE is therefore frequently discussed in the context of food security and rural development and is linked to the concept of food sovereignty. This concept is defined as “the right of people to healthy and culturally appropriate food produced through ecologically sound and sustainable methods, and their right to define their own food and agriculture systems, putting the aspirations and needs of those who produce, distribute and consume food at the heart of food systems and policies rather than the demands of markets and corporations”. Through this, AE is a voice of opposition to a neoliberal model of agriculture. AE is commonly linked to small-food producers that steward and guard the values of the territory and of ecosystem services, using socially fair and appropriate

technologies, with equitable trade at all levels (Tomlinson, 2013). While there are claims that AE is scalable, there is need for more knowledge and experience on how to achieve this (e.g. by increasing support from institutions, policy makers and the private sector), maintaining its typical characteristic of local solutions adapted to environmental, socioeconomic and cultural context.

5.3. Combined approaches for an effective transition to sustainable agriculture

Rather than looking at differences between approaches, there is a need to identify how different approaches like AE and SI can be complementary to facilitate their adoption and effectiveness towards more sustainable agriculture within the F2F, BS and SS, and to support other related policy goals like food security, social justice, and more prosperous rural areas and communities as foreseen in the LTVRA. Combined approaches based on integrated land use planning to optimize the delivery of ecosystem services can help to overcome many of the challenges to the transition to more sustainable agriculture. Various approaches to sustainable agriculture already adopt aspects, perspectives and strategies of AE and SI, adapting them to local conditions and possibilities (e.g. conservation agriculture, regenerative agriculture (Fig. 10) (Tiftonell et al., 2022), carbon farming, nature positive farming). Mixed models, taking advantage of the experiences in different farming approaches, incorporating scalable techniques of precision farming and conservation agriculture, could provide an advanced model of sustainable agriculture respecting the environment

Fig. 10. Green manure/cover under rainfed almond trees, a sustainable land management practice central to several agricultural approaches. Green manure and cover crop practices could help the transition from monocultures to diversified systems increasing biodiversity, improving soil properties and decreasing agricultural inputs, to help reaching objectives of the F2F, BS and SS of the Green Deal (Photo: Joris de Vente). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and social equity, and that together with changes in diet and reduced food waste, could result in a greener farming system that guarantees food security.

The challenge remains how to design integrated land use systems, combining SI and AE to provide synergies between both approaches and optimize the delivery of different ecosystem services to society respecting environmental limits. Currently, high input irrigated systems coexist with low input rainfed systems and are competing in unequal conditions (Fig. 11). The vast areas of high input and highly productive irrigated systems provide food and feed world-wide, but are also associated with externalities like serious on-site and off-site damage to ecosystems (Álvarez-Rogel et al., 2020). Often, these systems have grown at the expense of natural lands or traditional extensive rainfed agriculture that are less productive but have a strong potential to provide crucial regulating, supporting and cultural ecosystem services (Fig. 11). Now, the challenge is to move from these uncoupled competing farming systems to an integrated agricultural model that combines SI and AE in order to optimize delivery of provisioning, regulating, supporting and cultural ecosystem services. In this integrated model, the extensive, low input, farming systems require a further application of the principles of AE to fully unlock their potential to provide regulating, supporting and cultural ecosystem services (e.g. carbon sequestration, regulating water and sediment flows, increasing biodiversity, preserving cultural heritage, rural recreation potential services, spiritual values) and protect the well-being of rural population in multi-functional rural landscapes. On the other hand, the current intensive high input farming systems require a transition based on the genuine implementation of SI principles that optimize provisioning services (food and feed) with minimal environmental impacts. To make this integrated system work, collaboration and knowledge exchange between the extensive and intensive farming systems is required. Also integrated land use planning is needed to optimize the delivery of ecosystem services with minimal environmental and social externalities.

To facilitate the transition towards such an integrated farming system support at different levels is needed. First of all, the transition of the extensive farming systems requires support and compensation for the production of ecosystem services through effective “payments for ecosystem services” and other financing mechanisms that recognize their crucial role for society (Farley and Costanza, 2010; Kaiser et al.,

2021; Zabala et al., 2021; de Groot et al., 2022). Furthermore, the large scale implementation of sustainable farming practices in both extensive and intensive farming systems, requires support through public goods (e.g. rural infrastructure, storage facilities, machinery), research, credits, insurances, education and support to farmers’ organisations, cooperatives and extension services (e.g. farmer field schools, farmer to-farmer networks or community seed banks). Particularly extension services, farmer-to-farmer networks and participatory monitoring and evaluation in Living Labs are seen as crucial to support scaling of any sustainable farming approach (Tomlinson, 2013; Luján Soto et al., 2021a). Efforts to support scaling can build on the long standing experience of AE with this kind of processes to facilitate knowledge exchange and contribute to social learning (Luján Soto et al., 2021a). Moreover, experiences outside Europe that evidence how AE can provide increased yields while keeping high employment rates in the rural areas with a positive social impact can serve as an example for SI in Europe (Bernard and Lux, 2017). This can inspire actions within the F2F strategy and the LTVRA to achieve their goals, as well as supporting policies within the new CAP implementation at country level.

6. Conclusions

For the first time, several EU strategies and programs converge and put their focus on sustainable agriculture from different perspectives: The Farm to Fork strategy, the Biodiversity strategy and the Soil strategy 2030 from the Green Deal and furthermore the Long-Term Vision of EU Rural Areas, the new CAP, and the ‘EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe’. The different EU strategies and policies analysed here propose sustainable soil management as a tool to accomplish part of their objectives and reach sustainable agricultural systems. There seems to be a political, environmental and social momentum to promote a transition towards sustainable agriculture. However, moving from generic policy goals to the actual implementation and transition to a greener agriculture in Europe, that is respectful to other countries, the environment and to human and social rights regarding access to food and fair working conditions, remains highly complex and challenging and requires cross sectorial transdisciplinary collaboration.

The available tools to facilitate this transition to a greener agriculture are not completely defined, but several paths such as revising

Fig. 11. Conceptual model representing the transition from co-existence of uncoupled systems to multifunctional landscapes with synergies between different agroecosystems complementing each other and generating different services to the society in semiarid Mediterranean areas.

directives, applying climate and soil legislation, developing action plans and adapting the CAP are pointed out. In all those intentions, the role of farmers as managers of the ecosystems, preserving ecosystem services of different kind (regulating climate and hydrological fluxes, maintaining biodiversity and preserving cultural, historical and spiritual values) must be acknowledged, for example, through well designed payments for ecosystem services and innovative sustainable business models that together will help revitalizing rural areas and prevent rural abandonment.

Main challenges related to the transition to a greener agriculture include maintaining crop yields, fulfil crops nitrogen needs, land demand, changes in diet, reducing food waste and externalization. The diversity of these challenges clearly illustrates that the transition is not just a technical question of farming practices, but requires a holistic approach considering social, economic, cultural, technical and environmental aspects of the food system. For a transition to a greener food system, the changes in the production subsector must go parallel to a change in diet patterns, responsible consumption, reduction of food waste, access to sustainable food and environmental education.

Nowadays different sustainable farming initiatives co-exist and show many similarities with the concepts of sustainable intensification and agroecology. The development and implementation of integrated agroecology and sustainable intensification based farming systems, optimizing ecosystem services, building on collaboration, knowledge exchange and synergies is needed to foster large scale adoption and transition to sustainable farming. In these efforts, sustainable farming approaches should always be adapted to the local resources and environmental and socioeconomic conditions, building on local knowledge and collaboration, and valuing farmers as managers of agroecosystems and producers of ecosystem services. The Green Deal and other programs have developed policy objectives and a framework to facilitate this process, the challenge now is to move from policy to actual effective implementation maintaining close collaboration with all relevant sectors of civil society.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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